

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CAST SiC_p-AL COMPOSITES UNDER ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY: Several kinds of aluminum alloy matrix reinforced with silicon carbide particles had been prepared by casting route and tested at various temperatures and strain rates. By observation of composites' fracture microstructure, two fracture mode had been determined, namely cavity-coalescing type and interface-debonding type. In the testing range of present paper, main factor influencing fracture mode is strain rate. At lower strain rate, cavity could be well developed to be operating damage process, in which isolated cavity nucleated in the initial stage of deformation and preferentially grew along matrix grain boundaries to form microcracks; while interfacing debonding significantly occurred at higher strain rate, and interlinkage of adjacent debonded SiC-Al interface turned to be the predominant damage mechanism. The influence of temperature on transition of fracture mode might be indirect and needs further study.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, mechanical behavior at high temperature, fracture process, microstructure

INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, silicon carbide reinforced aluminum alloy matrix(SiC-Al) composite had demonstrated some favorable characteristics, including low raw material cost, easier control of the preparation process and less damage of reinforcement, property isotropy and machinability by conventional means. To examine the potential of such kind of materials to be applied under high temperature and to improve their workability, numerous research works had been done on the high temperature mechanical behavior of SiC-Al composites, especially on creep and superplasticity[1-3]. Meanwhile, SiC-Al composites could be manufactured at lower cost by employing casting route, however, research on cast SiC-Al composites' properties and microstructure under elevated temperature is in lack.

In the present paper, several kinds of SiC-Al composite prepared by compo-casting process had been tested under various temperature and strain rate, and the fracture microstructure was checked to determine the fracture characteristics of SiC-Al composite under elevated temperature and to reveal the role of SiC-Al interface.

EXPERIMENTAL

Composites employed in the present work were prepared by compo-casting route, in which SiC particles were added into solid-liquid state matrix alloy, followed by mechanical stirring and solidification. Ingots were then hot-pressed or extruded to reduce casting porosity, and machined to tensile specimens. Prior to testing, some specimen were heat treated to maintain microstructural stability during deformation, excepting the ones used for superplasticity testing ,where dynamic recrystallization was desired, and the 5083Al matrix material samples, which can not be strengthened by heat treatment. Testing and material parameters were summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Material and testing parameters

Testing Type	Temperature (°C)	Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	Material	Heat Treatment
Creep	300, 350	10 ⁻⁹ ~10 ⁻⁶	15 vol% SiC-2024Al	500°C, 1hr solution 190°C, 8hr aging
Superplasticity	~500	10 ⁻⁵ ~10 ⁻¹	10 vol% SiC-2024Al	none
Tension	200~400	~10 ⁻³	15 vol% SiC-5083Al 15 vol% SiC-5083Al-2Li	500°C, 1hr solution 150°C, 5hr aging (Li-containing ones only)

The microstructure of tested materials were examined using Hitachi S-520 SEM and Philips SEM515 SEM. In addition to fracture surface observation, more emphasis were put on sectioned microstructure analysis, in which specimens were sectioned along the longitudinal direction, then diamond polished and then slightly etched with a mixture of 0.5% HF, 1.5% HCl and 2.5% HNO₃.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fracture Microstructure of Creep Tested Specimen

The typical microstructure of creep tested composite is shown in Fig. 1. At a very low strain level, voids were found to appear at the grain boundaries perpendicular to the stress direction, which might be related to the directional diffusion of vacancies from the interior of grain to grain boundary[4]. As the strain increases, however, nucleating cavities were observed at the grain boundary triple points and about the interfacial coarse precipitates (Fig. 1(a)).

With creep time and macro strain further increasing, cavities began to grow, as shown in Fig. 1(b). It could be seen that the shape of cavities on the grain boundary and the coarse precipitate-matrix interface was elongated along the interface to form discontinuous microcracks, and that some new cavities nucleated within matrix. In a detailed quantitative work on creep cavitation, it was determined that the matrix cavities growth was controlled by diffusional mechanism during steady state creep of the SiC-Al composite[5]. It is interesting to note that the cavities on the SiC-Al interface still remained the original quasi-equiaxed shape.

Fig. 1(c) shows the prior-to-failure microstructure in the composite. In the case of the operation of a diffusion controlled growth mechanism, the grain boundary cavities eventually inter-linked to form microcracks along grain boundary, leading to final failure. Consequently, the SiC-Al interface was found to delay the propagation of grain boundary microcracks (Fig. 1(c)), indicating a high bonding strength between SiC particles and matrix.

*Fig.1: Fracture microstructure of 15vol% SiC-2024Al creep tested at 300°C and 29.4MPa
(a) Cavity nucleation; (b) Cavity growth; (c) Formation of microcrack*

Fracture Microstructure of Superplastically Tested Specimens

Fig. 2 shows the fracture microstructure of SiC-2024Al composite deformed at 495°C and $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to an elongation of about 150%, in which debonding of SiC-Al interface was found

to be the main feature. In Fig.2(a), it could be seen that a microcrack initialized in interfacial region was propagating to adjacent interface, indicating that the interface turned to be the preferential site of microcrack formation. Furthermore, microcracks were observed to propagate along SiC-Al interfaces and no evidence of matrix deformation in the area was found (Fig.2(b)), which hints significantly weakening of interface occurred during superplastic deformation. Compared to creep testing, the superplastic deformation temperature was much higher and near to that of matrix solidus point (502°C). Some researchers had reported interfacial solution element segregation and liquid phase was observed in superplastic composites [6, 7]. Therefore, it might be some kind of interfacial liquid phase that leading to interfacial weakening.

By the meantime, some cavities were also observed in regions of low SiC particle fraction, however, their size were smaller than that of those in creep tested specimens. Considering higher temperature and lower stress level compared to creep testing, it was reasonable to conclude during superplastic deformation the cavities still grew in diffusional mechanism, and hence the cavity growth rate was rather low to have significant impact on composite fracture process.

*Fig.2: Fracture microstructure of 10vol% SiC-2024Al composite superplastically deformed at 495°C and $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.
(a) Microcrack initialized in interfacial region; (b) Microcrack propagation*

Fracture Microstructure of Tension Tested Specimen

Fig.3 shows fracture microstructure of SiC-5083Al composites tensioned at 300°C and about 10^{-3} s^{-1} . In SiC-5083-2Li composite, where lithium was added to improve wetting between SiC particles and melted matrix alloy, reinforcement distributed uniformly. However, debonding of SiC-Al interface was observed, and adjacent debonded interfaces were found to linkup and form microcracks (Fig.3(a)).

Fig.3: Fracture microstructure of SiC-5083Al composite tensioned at 300°C and $\sim 10^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
 (a) SiC-5083Al-2Li; (b) SiC-5083Al

In 5083Al matrix material, SiC phases were severely segregated due to poor wetting and particle clusters were found to be the origin of crack formation. It is worth noting that microcrack propagated along matrix grain boundary was found to be stopped in front of isolated particle (Fig.3(b)).

For both materials, matrix cavities were observed. Compared with those found in crept specimens, their shape maintained equiaxial. The high deformation rate obviously hindered intensive development of matrix cavitation.

High Temperature Fracture Mode of Cast SiC-Al Composites

Based on above observation and analysis, fracture characteristics of cast SiC-Al composites under elevated temperature were summarized in Table 2. From these information, two fundamental fracture mode were determined. Under low strain rate (*e.g.* creep testing), cavitation intensively occurred, and the composite failed in cavity coalescence mode. While increasing strain rate (tension) or simultaneously increasing temperature (superplasticity), influence of matrix cavitation became minor and interface debonding turned to be dominating factor of composite failure. The two failure mode are illustrated in Fig. 4.

It could be found from Fig.4 that in the testing range of the present work, strain rate determined the fracture mode. Under elevated temperature, diffusion process is remarkable, and deformation difference between various material component at low strain rate could be accommodated by diffusion related process, for example, diffusion-controlled cavity growth under creep condition. While increasing strain rate, deformation difference between matrix and SiC reinforcement can not be accommodated by diffusional process and the composite failed by interface debonding. The role of deformation temperature in failure mode transition is not clear, might in an indirect way including variation of interfacial strength and matrix phase composition, and needs further study.

Table 2: Summary of fracture characteristics of cast SiC-Al composites under various high temperature deformation

Characteristics	Creep	Superplasticity	Tension
Fracture surface morphology	Ductile dimples with size near that of SiC particles, and tearing on SiC-Al interfaces	Cavities with size much larger than SiC particle radius	Ductile dimples with size near that of SiC particles, and tearing on some of SiC-Al interfaces
Damage mechanism	Cavitation occurred at matrix grain boundary, SiC-Al interface associated with coarse precipitates	Debonding of SiC-Al interface and cavitation on matrix grain boundary	Debonding of SiC-Al interface
Formation of microcracks	Linkup of cavities grew in diffusional mechanisms	Interlinkage of debonded interfaces	Interlinkage of debonded interfaces in SiC particle-aggregated area
Microcracks propagation path	Along matrix grain boundaries and matrix-precipitate interfaces, and well bonded SiC-Al interface resisted the propagation	Preferentially along SiC-Al interfaces	Along matrix grain boundaries and SiC-Al interfaces, and the interface resisted crack propagation under certain condition

Fig.4: Fracture mode determined in cast SiC-Al composites by present work

CONCLUSIONS

By observing fracture microstructure of several cast SiC-Al composites under elevated temperature, two fundamental fracture mode had been determined as cavity coalescence mode and interface debonding mode. Following conclusions were obtained:

1. In the testing range in present work, strain rate determined the fracture mode. Cavity coalescence mode occurred in the case of low strain rate, where main damage mechanism was cavitation within matrix, and cavities aggregated and interlinked to form microcracks leading to final failure. Interface debonding mode took place at higher strain rate, in which reinforcement-matrix interface debonded due to strain discrepancy or weakening of interface strength and hence linkuped to form microcracks.
2. Cavitation occurred during high temperature deformation of SiC-Al composites. Cavity nucleation was related to matrix precipitates, and the most preferential nucleating site were including triple points of matrix grain boundary, interjection of grain boundary and SiC-Al interface.
3. Influence of testing temperature on high temperature fracture process of SiC-Al composite might be indirect and needs further study.

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